

Drop Out of Girls in Higher Education: Special Reference to Vaijapur Tehsil Dist. Aurangabad (MS) India

Dr. Dnyaneshwar Khillari
Department of Marathi

Vinayakrao Patil Mahavidyalaya Vaijapur Dist. Aurangabad

Dr. Sheshrao Rathod (Associate Professor and Head)
Department of Sociology

Vinayakrao Patil Mahavidyalaya Vaijapur Dist. Aurangabad

Abstract:- Education is equal for all. Without any distinction between men and women, education can bring about social and cultural transformation along with personality development in them. But rural areas still have a high dropout rate of girls in graduate education or higher education. Vaijapur tehsil is no exception. The Vaijapur tehsil comes under permanently drought prone area. The purpose of the present research article is to study the dropout rate of girls in higher education in Vaijapur tehsil. Data was collected from 50 respondents from 10 villages through a survey questionnaire. The Shows result that, 62% respondents belong to open category. 96% of the respondents belonged to Hindu religion. 70% respondents said that our source of income is agriculture. 48% of male parent respondents said they have completed secondary education. 32% of male parent respondents said they have completed their higher secondary education. 52% female parent respondents said their education is up to primary. 42% female parent respondents said their education is up to secondary. 06% of the female parent respondents said that they have not completed graduation and post graduation. 58% of the respondents said that they have completed higher secondary education. 18% of the respondents said that they have completed their graduate education. 54% of the respondents said that they did not study because of the inconvenience of travel. 72% of the respondents said that getting married while still in education stopped further education. 50% of the respondents said that they could not pursue further education due to financial poverty. 44% of the respondents said that further education could not be completed due to family reluctance. 32% of respondents said they could not pursue further education due to vulnerability. 54% respondents said that further education was opposed by father. 44% of respondents said that education was opposed by mother. 38% of respondent's mothers support their education. 40% of the respondent's brothers support them to complete their education.

Keywords:- Girls Higher Education, Poverty, Dropout, Development.

I. INTRODACTION

In India everyone has equal opportunity for education. Although it is the government's responsibility to provide education opportunities to all, there is a need to change the social attitude towards girls' education. Getting access to primary, secondary and higher education for girls and not stopping their higher education is a major challenge in the context of higher education for rural girls today. The rights of women and the importance of their education are still not known at the society and family level. Even today, the birth of girls in rural areas is considered a stigma. Women in India are always considered as ours. In rural areas, girls do not get further education because their parents are illiterate. Along with this, many obstacles have education of girls. With that in mind, the dropout of girls in higher education in Vaijapur tahsil can be studied and its causes can be treated.

II. RSEARCH PROBLEM

The situation regarding education of girls is still not satisfactory. Not only in India but in the world, women are seen to have less opportunity for education for education, business and their development. Rural areas show more indifference in terms of higher education for women than urban areas. It can be seen that the secondary status of women to men is still there today. After higher secondary education, many girls are seen dropping out in higher education. As Vaijapur tehsil is a permanent drought area, there is also a dropout of girls in higher education. Therefore, dropout of girls in higher education is selected for the present topic of study.

➤ *Rsearch Objective*

- *To Study the Educational Status of Rural Girls.*
- *To Explore The Causes of Educational Dropout.*
- *Understanding Parents Attitudes Towards Girls Education.*

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- Kishor Bhattacharjee studied the Women's Education in Rural Bihar: Issues and Challenges. In the present article he concludes that the education of women in rural areas is still neglected. Rural women do all the work related to agriculture and do major work in the agriculture sector so they are deprived of education. In Bihar, insecurity of girl during their schooling, lack of drinking water, lack of toilets lack of teachers and withdrawal of girls from school for housework can be seen.
- Dr. Arati Pramod Sapkal, studied the Challenges in Higher Education. In this article they noted that, Improving access & quality of education at all levels, financial crises, privatization & modernization of education and system, poor technology, increasing the literacy rate, lack of autonomy, poor evaluation system, low quality of research, perfect recruitment, placement & promotion of faculty, self- financing colleges, Academic & Administrative reforms, improper implementation of government policies & programmers in higher education, syllabus is not job oriented or mismatch between the demand & content of the curriculum etc. These are the challenges facing higher education in India.
- Prof. Lata Gupte studied Women and Indian Higher Education, the following findings are reported in the present article, and the cost of higher education is depriving the common class of it. The principle of equality is not followed in education and the education of boys is given priority over girls and due to this girls lag behind in education. In today's situation, women's education is hindered due to many problems such as family, society's attitude towards women, social problems and women's safety while getting higher education.
- M. Aamin, Mohammad Islam studied what supports females In Higher Education progression? A Pakistani Public University Context. He reported the following findings in his article. Women's higher education is very less in developing countries including Pakistan. When he studied the barriers to women's advancement in higher education, it highlighted the main reasons as ignorant parents, cultural norms, low socioeconomic status, and unavailability of universities in remote areas, and traditional mentality, ideology of the family. Besides, early marriage of girls, misunderstanding of Islam, customs and values, conservatism are cited as barriers to higher education for women.
- M. Sowjanya S. Shetty, Ramesh Salian studied the women's Access to Higher Education in India. The statistics for the year 2015-16 are given in respect of women's higher education degree and post-graduate education. Enrollment is 86% at undergraduate level and fewer enrollments at postgraduate level is 11.9%. Overall participation of women in postgraduate higher education and research is reported to be very low. In this context, various obstacles faced by women in higher education have been recorded here. It mainly includes gender inequality, conservative mentality, early marriage. Family restrictions, limited access to quality education in rural areas, long distance colleges, etc., are suggested to be the reasons.
- A. Selwan studied the Problems of Rural Girl Students in Higher Educational Institution. In the present article they report the following conclusions. It is felt that provision of locally relevant high quality education and training opportunities is essential to retain rural girls in higher educational institutions. It has been opined that various prejudices create both structural and attitudinal barriers for girls in rural areas to pursue higher education. There is no positivity towards higher education of girls in rural areas. Early marriage, illiteracy of parents, lack of educational facilities in rural areas, various responsibilities of women at home, etc., are the reasons for the low enrollment of girls in higher education.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The present article tries to investigate the causes of girl's dropout in higher education in rural Vaijapur. For this purpose the data has been collected from 50 respondents of 10 villages through survey questionnaires. The other useful study material was downloaded from the respective websites, books and journals.

➤ Data Analysis

Table 1 Demographic Profile of Respondents

S No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Category		
	OPEN	31	62%
	OBC	09	18%
	SC	04	10%
	NT	06	12%
2	Income source		
	Farming	35	70%

	Occupation	03	06%
	Service	01	02%
	Farming & Wages	11	22%
3	Father Education		
	Primary	08	16%
	Secondary	24	48%
	Hr. Secondary	16	32%
	UG	02	04%
	PG	00	00%
4	Mother Education		
	Primary	26	52%
	Secondary	21	42%
	Hr. Secondary	03	06%
	UG	00	00%
	PG	00	00%
5	Religion		
	Hindu	48	96%
	Islam	02	04%
	Buddhist	00	00%

Table No 1 shows the demographical profile of respondents. 62% respondents belong to open category. 18% respondents belong to OBC category. 10% respondents belong to SC and 12% respondents belong to NT category. 70% respondents said that our source of income is agriculture. 22% respondents said their source of income is farming and labor. 48% of male parent respondents said they have completed secondary education. 32% of male parent respondents said they have completed their higher secondary education. Whereas 16% male parent respondents said that our primary education is complete. 52% female parent respondents said their education is up to primary. 42% female parent respondents said their education is up to secondary. 06% of the female parent respondents said that they have not completed graduation and post graduation. 96% of the respondents belonged to Hindu religion. 04% of the respondents belonged to Islam.

Table 2 Education of the Girl's Respondent

S No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Education		
	Primary	2	04%
	Secondary	10	20%
	Hr. Secondary	29	58%
	UG	09	18%
	PG	00	00%
2	Total	50	100%

Table No 2 shows the Education of the girl's respondent. 4% of the respondents said that they have completed primary education. 20% of respondents said that they have completed secondary education. 58% of the respondents said that they have completed higher secondary education. 18% of the respondents said that they have completed their graduate education. So none of the respondents have completed post graduate.

Table 3 Reasons for Dropping Out of Education

S No	Reasons	Frequency	Percentage
1	Inconvenience of travel	27	54%
2	Marriage	36	72%
3	Agricultural work/ House work	17	34%
4	Poverty	25	50%
5	Teasing	6	12%
6	Unaccompanied by a girl	8	16%
7	Family reluctance	22	44%
8	Vulnerability	16	32%
	Total	50	100%

Table No 3 shows reasons for dropping out of education. 54% of the respondents said that they did not study because of the inconvenience of travel. 72% of the respondents said that getting married while still in education stopped further education. 34% of the respondents said that parents stopped education due to farm work as well as housework. 50% of the respondents said that they could not pursue further education due to financial poverty. 12% respondents said that parents stop further education due to

teasing during travel and other places. 16% of the respondents said that education stopped because there was no one to accompany them from village to taluka for college education. 44% of the respondents said that further education could not be completed due to family reluctance. 32% of respondents said they could not pursue further education due to vulnerability.

Table 4 Someone from your Family was Strongly Opposed to your Education

S No	Relative	Frequency	Percentage
1	Father	27	54%
2	Mother	22	44%
3	Brother	8	16%
4	Grandparents	17	37%
5	Other Relatives	15	33%
	Total	50	100%

Table No 4 shows strong opposition to education from family members. 54% respondents said that further education was opposed by father. 44% of respondents said that education was opposed by mother. 16% respondents said that there was opposition from brother for further education. 37% respondents said that opposition from grandparents stopped further education. 33% respondents said that education was discontinued due to opposition from other relative.

Table 5 Who Had A Strong Desire to Complete your Education

S No	Relative	Frequency	Percentage
1	Father	16	32%
2	Mother	19	38%
3	Brother	20	40%
4	Grandparents	05	10%
5	Other Relatives	04	08%
	Total	50	100%

Table No. shows who had a strong desire to complete your education. 32% fathers support their daughter to complete her education. 38% of respondent's mothers support their education. 40% of the respondent's brothers support them to complete their education. 10% of the respondent's grandparents support their education. While 08% other relatives support respondents education.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *After the Observation of the Dropout in Graduate Education in Vijapur Tehsil we have Some Findings there are Followings.*

- 62% respondents belong to open category.
- 96% of the respondents belonged to Hindu religion.
- 70% respondents said that our source of income is agriculture.
- 48% of male parent respondents said they have completed secondary education. 32% of male parent respondents said they have completed their higher secondary education.
- 52% female parent respondents said their education is up to primary. 42% female parent respondents said their education is up to secondary. 06% of the female parent respondents said that they have not completed graduation and post graduation
- 58% of the respondents said that they have completed higher secondary education. 18% of the respondents said that they have completed their graduate education.
- 54% of the respondents said that they did not study because of the inconvenience of travel.
- 72% of the respondents said that getting married while still in education stopped further education.
- 50% of the respondents said that they could not pursue further education due to financial poverty.

- 44% of the respondents said that further education could not be completed due to family reluctance. 32% of respondents said they could not pursue further education due to vulnerability.
- 54% respondents said that further education was opposed by father. 44% of respondents said that education was opposed by mother.
- 38% of respondent's mothers support their education. 40% of the respondent's brothers support them to complete their education.

VI. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In the 10 villages selected for the research, it was seen that the proportion of open category and Maratha community was the majority. Almost 70% of families are dependent on agriculture. Those who are small landholders earn their living by farming and labour. Most of the fathers of the respondents have completed secondary and higher secondary education. Only 04% of fathers have completed degree education. The mother of the respondent has only completed primary and secondary education. Mother's higher secondary education was found to be very less as compared to fathers' of the respondents. 20% of girls' education has stopped after secondary education. Whereas 58% of girls' education has stopped after higher secondary education. Only 18% of girls have completed girls have completed graduate education and none have completed postgraduate education.

The reasons for dropout of girls in higher education would have been explored. It was found that 72% of girl's education stopped due to early marriage. 54% of respondents could not complete further education due to inconvenience of travel. 50% of the respondents could not pursue higher education due to financial poverty. Along with this, it seems that the dropout rate of girls in higher education has increased due to lack of desire of family, agricultural work, housework, teasing by boys on the road or while traveling. Insecurity, differentiate between boys and girls, traditional attitude of parents. Due to traditional mentality of mothers, fathers and relatives, even today it seems that girls are opposed to education. However, educated parents and special brothers seem to support the girl's education.

RECOMMENDATION

- There is a need to create public awareness among illiterate and semi-educated parents in rural areas regarding higher education of girls.
- It is necessary to increase the number of independent women's colleges in rural areas for higher education of girls.
- College should provide free hostel for girls pursuing higher education.
- It is necessary to create awareness so that parents do not marry girls early after secondary education.
- It is necessary to create a safe environment for girls coming from rural areas to cities for higher education while traveling and in college.
- It is necessary to change the family and social attitude regarding higher education of girls in rural areas.

➤ *Consent*

As per international standard or university standard, respondent's written consent has been collected and preserved by the authors(s).

➤ *Acknowledgemnt*

The author is grateful to Principal Vinayakrao Patil MahavidyalayaVaijapur and UGC-STRIDE Scheme Component-1 for final support during this Student Project. We also express thanks to our Students Pawar Varsha Bhaskar & Pawar Poonam Navnath B. A. T. Y

➤ *Competing Intrersts*

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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